

A Mathematical Model for Percentile and Rank Estimation in Competitive Examinations and its Analogy with Statistical Mechanics

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ABSTRACT

Assessing student performance and making decisions regarding college admissions heavily rely on percentile estimation. In this work, a basic mathematical model for evaluating the probability of syllabus coverage and corresponding marks has been developed. Based on the students' preparation level, we have defined empirical expressions for estimating the percentile and ranks of the students. Furthermore, we derive equations for the mean, standard deviation, and most probable marks. To account for the role played by negative marking in such examinations, we have modified our model to incorporate its effect. A crucial component of this model is the difficulty parameter whose effect is profound in the entire model. The findings have been schematically represented and then compared with real data graphically. Additionally, we graphically compare our model to a statistical mechanics-based approach, establishing their equivalence. Our results demonstrate that percentile growth is non-linear, with small change in marks leading to large percentile shifts. External factors like paper difficulty and normalization techniques are indicated by deviations from theoretical expectations. These insights can improve the accuracy of percentile predictions and guide preparation techniques for competitive exams.

Keywords: Percentile Estimation, Syllabus Coverage, Negative Marking, Difficulty Parameter, Statistical Mechanics, Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution, JEE Mains, Normalization Process, Rank Estimation, Preparation Index

1. Introduction

All over the country, there are several examinations that take place that use the normalization method to convert the raw score of individuals to percentiles. The percentiles obtained in these examinations by students determine the fates of the students to get into a particular college for a particular course of study. Percentile ascertains the position of a student relative to the performance of other students appearing for these evaluations. Examinations like JEE Mains, JEE Advanced, CUET UG, UGC NET, etc. conduct exams in various sessions and over a period of time instead of a single day, for which different papers are prepared. No matter the steps taken, there still lies an ambiguity of the difficulty of exam across different sessions which might lead to skewed results. Here, the abbreviation UGC stands for University Grant Commission and NET stands for National Eligibility Test. The students who attempt difficult paper sets might end up getting lower scores as compared to the students who are writing easier set of questions, which is unfair to the motive of various testing agencies conducting the exams. In order to overcome such difficulties, "Normalization process" is conducted based on Percentile Scores. The procedure of Normalization is a standardized process for comparing the marks obtained by the students across different sessions and the same practice is followed for a large number of exams throughout.

An apt example of how the normalization works can be seen in the Joint Entrance Examination (JEE) Mains conducted by National Testing Agency (NTA). As stated by NTA in its official website, the percentile score of a student is the number of students obtaining the percentage equals to or less than the percentage of that particular student [1]. CUET UG (Central University Entrance Test Undergraduate) has an entire section in its information bulletin published on its official website which explains this Equi-Percentile method in great detail. Then instead of using the raw scores, the percentile scores are used to rank the students, based on which the students are given entry into various colleges all across the country [2]. This kind of ranking scheme is also used for assessments carried out by Institute of Banking Personnel Selection (IBPS) for banking positions [3].

Although the procedure for formulation of the percentile scores has been revealed on various websites but it still stands a very complex procedure. The simple reason being that the raw scores and percentile data is not released by these testing agencies and there is no way for the students to get hold of their raw scores. Moreover, there are innumerable examinees taking such assessments and until and unless it is a professional, it is very difficult for general public to handle such huge amount of data even if the data had been handy for us, which is again a hypothetical situation. Therefore, it is crucial to comprehend and analyse these normalization processes since they enable us to better understand how educators can manage the student body and forecast student performance based on preparation level. The paper's analysis can also provide feedback on the degree of difficulty of exam papers and inform those who create them about the need for more standardized questions.

The motivation behind the work has been taken from the papers written by one of the authors of the present article, Sudipto Roy. In his model, a straightforward mathematical model has been established that can be used to calculate a student's percentile and, consequently, their rank based on the

grades they receive in an exam [4]. The entire test has been broken up into sections of comparable complexity and preparation time. As a result, the marks have been developed as a percentage function. The percentile has been provided as a probability function of the percentage of marks based on widely accepted observations. Given the significant role negative marking plays in all of these exams, it has also been taken into account in our scheme. Additionally, after negative marking was added to the model, the percentile and ranks of the students were represented mathematically as the probability functions of marks they received.

In another paper by Sudipto Roy, he has considered the student's marks to be known, and has developed a method to estimate the percentile score [5]. Calculating the most likely marks and their associated probability is made simpler by using the marks $f(m)$ as a probability function. The likelihood of receiving marks within the range provided by m may therefore be determined with the aid of a cumulative probability $g(m)$ of the number of students who will receive marks greater than or equal to m . We will represent our model graphically by changing various parameters like difficulty level, etc. to understand the implications of these parameters on our model.

This project is driven by the need to develop a model which is based on statistical mechanics so that the principles from the same can be utilized to make more precise percentile estimation. This knowledge can be used to a more effective preparation strategy and help the academic instructors to ensure fairness. In order to do so, the Maxwell Boltzmann distribution can be used to study the distribution of marks, considering the similarity that can be drawn between the distribution of particles in different energy levels and the distribution of students across different marks in the entire range; and between the students and the particles in an ensemble. In such a model, the percentile can be taken as a cumulative probability, and finally, ranks can also be expressed in terms of marks. Since NTA and other testing organizations do not supply any of their raw data, we have drawn model real-world data using readily available data from sites such as Careers360, Shiksha, and BYJUs. This allows the graphs produced by our model to be compared to the data that was initially derived from the actual student scores and percentiles.

2. Model Formulation

In this model, the case of JEE Mains has been specifically considered to simplify the model. In JEE Mains (abbreviated for Joint Entrance Examination) consists of 75 questions in total. Each correct answer is awarded with +4 marks whereas the incorrect answer gets the students a -1 (minus one), thus the maximum marks that can be obtained is 300 and the minimum marks is -75 (minus seventy-five). JEE Mains is conducted by NTA in two sessions and over different shifts. After the exam is conducted NTA releases an answer key which enables the students to estimate their raw scores but since the percentile calculation is a very complex procedure, the students look into various sites to estimate their percentile and ranks based on the former. This paper focuses on estimating the percentile of students based on the marks, as per the method mentioned by the NTA in its official website. Moreover, a direct correlation can be established between the portions of syllabus completed to the estimated percentile obtained.

2.1 Syllabus Coverage

Let the entire syllabus for the examination be divided into N equal parts where equality of the parts is determined by different factors like importance, length of portion, difficulty, etc. The probability that a student covers x parts of the syllabus is defined by a function $f(x)$ such that

$$f(x) = \frac{a}{b^x} \quad (01)$$

where x is a discrete random variable that runs from 0 to N

Since $f(x)$ is probability distribution function, it will always have value from 0 to 1 (both inclusive) for all possible values of x .

To meet this requirement, we must have $0 < a < 1$ and $b > 1$. The function $f(x)$ has been so chosen because of the observation that as the number of syllabus portions increases, the chances of a student covering those portions should decrease. In other words, as x increases, $f(x)$ is likely to decrease.

Since the sum of probabilities for all possible values of x is 1,

$$\sum_{x=0}^N f(x) = 1 \quad (02)$$

Substituting from equation (1) into equation (2), we get,

$$\sum_{x=0}^N \frac{a}{b^x} = 1 \quad (03)$$

Equation (3) leads to the following value of a [6-8].

$$a = \frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1} \quad (04)$$

As per equation (4), for an extremely large values of N , $a \approx 1 - \frac{1}{b}$

Using equation (4) in equation (1), we get,

$$f(x) = \frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1} b^{-x} \quad (05)$$

where $x = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$

For larger values of b , $f(x)$ decreases faster as x increases.

2.2 Percentile Evaluation

Let the total number of students who have appeared for the examination be Y .

Number of students who have prepared x out of N parts of the syllabus can be represented by $y(x)$ as,

$$y(x) = Y f(x) \quad (06)$$

Marks of a student can be considered as a function of portions of the syllabus covered. If other parameters like the performance of students on the day of exam, the time limit, the difficulty level of the exam are ignored, then we can say that, as more parts of syllabus is covered, more questions would be attempted and therefore the marks of the student would increase.

Using the percentile definition from NTA website which states that

$$\text{Percentile of a student} = \frac{\text{Number of students who have scored less than or equal to the marks obtained by the student}}{\text{Total number of students}} \times 100$$

From this definition we can infer that the percentile of a student, who has covered x portions of the syllabus, can be taken to be the ratio of the number of students covering x or less portions to the total number of students taking the examination. We consider marks (obtained by a student) to be proportional to the number of portions covered by the student.

Therefore, the percentile score P is,

$$P = \frac{\sum_0^x y(x)}{Y} \times 100 \quad (07)$$

Using equation (6) in equation (7), we get,

$$P = \frac{\sum_0^x Y f(x)}{Y} \times 100 = 100 \times \sum_0^x f(x) \quad (08)$$

Using equation (5) in equation (8), we get,

$$P = 100 \times \sum_0^x \frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1} b^{-x} \quad (09)$$

Using the formula for sum of geometric series on the term b^{-x} [6-8], the expression for P becomes,

$$P = 100 \times \left(\frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1} \right) \left(\frac{b - b^{-x}}{b - 1} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\text{For large values of } N, P \approx 100 \times (1 - b^{-x-1}) \quad (11)$$

In Figure-1, we have plotted the percentile (P) of the student against its preparation index ($K = x/N$) using the equation (12). As the preparation index increases, the percentile increases at a gradually slower rate. As b increases, the percentile rises faster with K , getting closer to 100 more rapidly.

2.3 Preparation Index

Let us now introduce another parameter, called the *preparation index* K , which can be defined as the ratio of the number of parts studied by a student (let x) to the total number of parts present in the syllabus, i.e. $K = \frac{x}{N}$

In terms of the aforementioned parameter, we can rewrite equation (10) as

$$P = 100 \times \left(\frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1} \right) \left(\frac{b - b^{-KN}}{b - 1} \right) \quad (12)$$

Similarly for extremely large values of N when $b^{N+1} \gg 1$, we can write equation (12) as

$$P \approx 100 \times (1 - b^{-KN-1}) \quad (13)$$

2.4 Role of Negative Marking

In most of the competitive examinations that are held on an All-India basis, negative marking scheme has a major role to play. They penalize the students for every wrong answer thus discouraging students from randomly guessing answers.

Let the total number of questions be S . We know that K is the fraction of the syllabus covered by a student; thus KS is can be regarded as approximately the number of questions attempted by the student ignoring other factors like the mental state of a student in the exam hall, the time constraint, and other complex parameters. Now, let us introduce another parameter g such that $1/g$ is the difficulty level of the exam. Easier the paper, the parameter g gets closer to 1. Therefore, we can write gKS be the total number of questions that has been attempted correctly by any student where $0 < g \leq 1$. The number of questions that has not been answered correctly by the student will then become $(1 - g)KS$. Let us assume that a student gets $+p$ for every correct answer and $-q$ for every wrong answer (with $p, q > 0$). Total marks (or *full marks*) of the paper is thus pS .

Marks (m) secured by a student with preparation index $K (= x/N)$ is therefore given by,

$$m = pgKS - q(1 - g)KS \quad (14)$$

Percentage of marks obtained by the student is,

$$M = 100 \times \frac{pgKS - q(1 - g)KS}{pS} = 100 \times K \left[g - \frac{q}{p} (1 - g) \right] \quad (15)$$

Using equation (15) we write,

$$K = \frac{M}{100 \times \left[g - \frac{q}{p} (1 - g) \right]} \quad (16)$$

Using equation (16) in (12) we get,

$$P = 100 \times \left(\frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{b - 1} \right) \left(b - b^{-\frac{NM}{100 \times \left[g - \frac{q}{p} (1 - g) \right]}} \right) \quad (17)$$

Equation (17) is an expression of percentile (P) in terms of percentage of marks M .

We have plotted equation (17) in the following graphs which basically plots the percentile of a student against his percentage of marks. Thus we have studied the role of parameters like N , b and g , in governing the nature of these plots.

Figure-2 studies the effect of change of b . For higher values of b , the value of P increases faster as a function of M .

Figure 3: Plot of percentile (P) versus marks (M) for three values of N , $b=1.075$, $p=4$, $q=1$, $g=1$

Figure-3 highlights the plot of percentile versus marks percentage for different values of N to understand the effect of change of N on the percentile trend. The percentile plots become steeper as N rises.

2.5 Rank Calculation

The entire scheme for percentile estimation has been modelled so as to understand how the ranking scheme of such examination works on the basis of which students get themselves enrolled in different institutes.

The number of candidates who have scored marks less than or equal to the student whose percentile score is P , can be written as $YP/100$. The number of students who have secured marks greater than the student is $Y - YP/100$.

Thus, expected rank (R) of the student is given by,

$$R = Y \left(1 - \frac{P}{100}\right) = \frac{Y}{100} (100 - P) \quad (18)$$

Using equation (17) in (18), we get,

$$R = Y \left(1 - \left(\frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1}\right) \left(\frac{1}{b-1}\right) \left(b - b^{-\frac{NM}{100 \times \left[\frac{g}{p}(1-g)\right]}}\right)\right) \quad (19)$$

Hence, we have now obtained the expression for rank of a student (R) in terms of the percentage of marks (M).

Instead of using rank directly for evaluation of the performance of students, we can take the factor R/Y as a more accurate parameter to assess the performance of the students. Since R/Y gives the achievement of the student relative to the other students, it is more meaningful to use this parameter instead of using the rank directly.

$$\frac{R}{Y} = \left(1 - \left(\frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1}\right) \left(\frac{1}{b-1}\right) \left(b - b^{-\frac{NM}{100 \times \left[\frac{g}{p}(1-g)\right]}}\right)\right) \quad (20)$$

Figure 4: Plot of R/Y (relative ranking) versus Marks (M) for three values of N , $b=1.075$, $p=4$, $q=1$, $g=1$

Figure-4 shows plots of R/Y as a function of marks percentage (M) for three values of N . As M increases, R/Y decreases for all N . As N increases, the value of N/Y falls faster with M .

Figure 5: Plot of Rank/Total number of students (R/Y) versus Marks (M) for three different values of b , $n=100$, $p=4$, $q=1$, $g=1$

Figure-5 shows plots of R/Y as a function of marks percentage (M) for three values of b . As M increases, R/Y decreases for all b . As b increases, the value of N/Y falls faster with M .

Using the expressions of the percentile and rank, we can calculate the unknown parameters in the model N , b , g based on the marks, rank and percentile that has been collected from the data of the previous examinations.

The mean value of x and x^2 are given by $\mu(x) = \sum_{x=0}^N x f(x)$ and $\mu(x^2) = \sum_{x=0}^N x^2 f(x)$. The standard deviation of x is given as $\sigma(x) = \sqrt{\sum_{x=0}^N f(x)(x - \mu)^2} = \sqrt{\mu(x^2) - [\mu(x)]^2}$ [6-8].

Based on equation (5), we can write,

$$\mu(x) = \left(\frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{b} + \frac{2}{b^2} + \frac{3}{b^3} + \dots + \frac{N}{b^N} \right) \tag{21}$$

$$\sigma(x) = \left[\frac{\left(\frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{b} + \frac{4}{b^2} + \frac{9}{b^3} + \dots + \frac{N^2}{b^N} \right)}{\left\{ \left(\frac{b^{N+1} - b^N}{b^{N+1} - 1} \right) \left(\frac{1}{b} + \frac{4}{b^2} + \frac{9}{b^3} + \dots + \frac{N^2}{b^N} \right) \right\}^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (22)$$

We know, preparation index $K = x/N$, we can write $\mu(K) = \mu(x)/N$ and $\sigma(K) = \sigma(x)/N$

The marks percentage is, $M = 100 \times K \left[g - \frac{q}{p} (1 - g) \right]$

The mean and standard deviation of M , denoted by $\mu(M)$ and $\sigma(M)$, respectively, can be expressed as,

$$\mu(M) = 100 \times \mu(K) \left[g - \frac{q}{p} (1 - g) \right] \quad (23)$$

$$\mu(M) = 100 \times \frac{\mu(x)}{N} \left[g - \frac{q}{p} (1 - g) \right] \quad (24)$$

$$\sigma(M) = 100 \times (\sigma(x))/N \left[g - \frac{q}{p} (1 - g) \right] \quad (25)$$

Thus, we have successfully established a model which can estimate the percentile and rank of the student if the marks are known. The marks can be calculated from the answer key that NTA releases before it declares its results. The unknown parameters associated with the model can be calculated if only enough data can be obtained which at the moment, is not available to us.

2.6 Calculations when percentile is known

If we observe the general trend of competitive examinations, we will find that the percentile score increases with increase in the marks, and the rate of its change (with marks) decreases with increase in marks. Using this pure observation, we are proposing an empirical expression for Percentile Score P ,

$$P(m) = a[1 - \exp\{-b(m+c)\}]^n \quad (26)$$

where $a, b, c, n > 0$.

The reason why such a function is chosen is because of the facts that we have observed, $P(m)$ increases with m , approaching the value of a asymptotically. For larger values of n , the rate of increase of $P(m)$ (with m) decreases slowly.

Since for simplification we are specifically considering the case of JEE Mains, we can take the total marks of the entire paper as 300. The corresponding percentile $P(m)$ should be 100 (highest possible percentile score) for $m = 300$. Using this, we can write equation (26) as,

$100 = a[1 - \exp\{-b(300+c)\}]^n$, which leads to,

$$a = \frac{100}{[1 - \exp\{-b(300+c)\}]^n} \quad (27)$$

Using equation (27) in (26), we get,

$$P(m) = \frac{100[1 - \exp\{-b(m+c)\}]^n}{[1 - \exp\{-b(300+c)\}]^n} \quad (28)$$

Nobody scores marks for which the percentile score is zero. The lowest marks that can be obtained is $m = -c + 1$, as zero percentile is obtained when $m = -c$ from equation (26), since marks increases by 1. Finding a certain combination of values for the constant parameters (b , c , and n) is necessary to guarantee the accuracy of the results produced by this formula (equation 28). While doing any analysis based on equation (28), one should use those values m that falls in the range given by $-c + 1 < m \leq 300$, to avoid unacceptable results or behaviour for $P(m)$.

By definition, percentile score of a student is the percentage of students getting marks less than or equal to that of the student. Thus, the percentage of students getting exactly m marks will be calculated as $P(m) - P(m-1)$. Hence, the fraction of students getting exactly m marks can be expressed as:

$$F(m) = \frac{P(m) - P(m-1)}{100} \quad (29)$$

Using equation (28) in (29), we get,

$$F(m) = \frac{[1 - \exp\{-b(m+c)\}]^n - [1 - \exp\{-b(m-1+c)\}]^n}{[1 - \exp\{-b(300+c)\}]^n} \quad (30)$$

Figure 6: Plot of Percentile versus Marks for $b = 0.032502$, $c = -13.530458$, $n = 1.602279$. This graph highlights the real data as the blue points and the red line is the fitted curve

Figure 7: Plot of Probability of obtaining Marks $F(m)$ versus Marks (m) .

Figure-6 shows the percentile versus marks plot for the data that has been collected from real sources. The different shades of blue data points signify the density of percentile across the marks. This has been done because the data points are huge in number and on plotting them; it becomes very dense to actually interpret. The red line is the best fit line of equation (28) to the data. The parameter values obtained by curve fitting are, $b = 0.032502$, $c = -13.530458$, $n = 1.602279$.

Figure-7 shows the probability of obtaining marks m versus marks as given in equation (30). This shows that most of the students score marks in this range whereas the graph towards the two extremes converges to zero showing that there is a very small percentage of students in the two extreme ranges. Thus, the graph follows an asymmetric bell-shaped curve which we will see as the kind of behaviour for real data. The peak value of marks is at 39.3, which is the most probable marks. The number of students obtaining that score can be calculated as follows: if the number of students taking part in the exam is 10^6 , then, based on $F(m = 39.31) = 0.093684$, number of students scoring 39.31 is $0.093684 \times 10^6 = 93,684$.

We can consider $F(m)$ as the probability of the students obtaining m marks because of the large sample size. Here, m can be taken as a random variable in the range $-c + 1 < m \leq 300$. By using equation (30), it is found that for $n \leq 1$, $F(m)$ is a monotonically decreasing function of m , with the lowest possible marks, $m = -c + 1$, corresponding to the highest value of $F(m)$. When $n > 1$, $F(m)$ peaks at a certain value of m , which could be thought of as the most likely scores for the test takers. The lowest possible scores cannot actually be the most likely grades since no applicant is supposed to go into the test knowing nothing or feeling compelled to try questions for which they have no idea how to answer them, which would result

in a low score. Consequently, the range of values $n \leq 1$ is not acceptable for the parameter n . It is evident that as n rises, so does the most likely value of m .

3. Analogy with Statistical Mechanics

3.1 Portion of the Syllabus Covered

Considering a system of students appearing for JEE Mains (for simplicity, we are specifically considering the case) can be compared to system of particles. In that case the marks that can be obtained by the students within the range from -75 to 300 can be taken as a microstate. Then the rank and the percentile calculation can be considered to be macro-states since these properties define the entire system and can be only calculated if we take the entire system into consideration. Now since the students of the system are not interacting with each other we can consider the system to be made of ideal gases instead of real gases. Using the property of ideal gas when they collide with each other, the collisions are purely elastic i.e., there is no exchange of energy between them. Similarly in our model there is no interaction between the different systems.

Now let us assume that the entire syllabus is divided into equal parts (the equality being decided upon by factors like difficulty, number of questions in that part, time of preparation). Just like we discussed earlier, it is not possible for all students to complete the entire syllabus. Let us define a parameter $p(x)$ as the probability of students who can complete x parts of the syllabus. We can then write $p(x)$ as [9-11],

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-\beta E(x)} \quad (31)$$

Here $E(x)$ is the effort energy required to prepare a particular x portion of the syllabus. Since the effort energy increases with increase in the portions that have to be covered, we can say that $E(x) = \alpha x$, where α is a positive constant. Thus, equation (32) becomes,

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{Z} e^{-\beta \alpha x} \quad (32)$$

The partition function is defined here as $Z = \sum_N e^{-\beta E(x)}$ [9-11]. This is similar to the partition function used by Maxwell Boltzmann in defining his model that explains the number of particles present in different microstates of same energy. Since $\sum_N p(x) = 1$, we introduce the term $\sum_N e^{-\beta E(x)}$ which ensures this requirement. Thus $\sum_N e^{-\beta E(x)}$ helps us to normalize the function.

We also know that the difficulty of the paper is a very important parameter in determining the percentile of the students. Same amount of preparation can also lead to obtain different percentiles considering the fact that more the difficult the exam is, lesser will be the number of students who can attempt greater sections of paper and hence, score higher marks. This is taken care of by the parameter β which is the difficulty level of exam. Greater the value of β , students are more likely to score lower marks as compared to for a lower value of β . Temperature plays an equivalent role in distributing the particles in different energy states. Lesser number of particles exists in energy states at higher temperatures.

Figure 8: Plot of Probability of covering the Syllabus Sections against Syllabus Sections for different values of β

Figure-8 shows the probability of coverage of x parts of the syllabus, as a function of the variable x . We analyse the effect of different values of β on the graph. As the value of β increases, there is a steeper fall of $p(x)$ with x .

Hence, students behave like particles and the amount of syllabus covered can be considered analogous to different energy levels. The distribution of students across the various values of x (portions of syllabus) is similar to that of the distribution of particles across different energy levels. Thus, the distribution function follows a Boltzmann curve where β is the difficulty level of the exam and has inverse relation to temperature. Just like only a very few particles occupy the higher energy levels, a very few students cover the entire syllabus. Most of the students cover a moderate amount of syllabus

while few students cover almost nothing. This helps us to draw the similarity between the Boltzmann curve and the behaviour of our model. For high β , very few students cover the entire syllabus but for low value of β , students prepare syllabus more uniformly.

3.2 Marks Distribution

A student scores marks depending on his performance on the day of assessment. Assuming that the distribution is evenly distributed would mean that every student has received equal marks, which is not possible. The ones who have prepared seriously tend to obtain more marks than those who have prepared less extensively, provided that other factors like panic, confidence are not affecting their state to perform in the exams. Moreover, if we compare a real data graph [shown in Figure 9], we will find that the graph is bell-shaped and skewed with a long tail towards the high marks' region. Figure-9 depicts the probability $P(m)$ versus marks m based on the data for JEE (Mains) obtained from certain sources [12, 13]. This shows that number of students obtaining lesser marks is more prominent than the number of students who have obtained higher marks. There is a certain mark or several certain marks that will have definitely the most probability of occurrence. There is another fact that can be seen from the real data graph – the distribution does not start to increase directly at zero. There is a certain probability of obtaining negative marks but students do not obtain -75 in any of the data that we could get our hands on. This can be representative of the fact that neither any student goes unprepared to the exam nor attempts all questions wrong.

For a more difficult exam, the graph becomes more skewed such that fewer students score high marks but when the exam is easier, the

Figure 9: Marks Distribution (Probability of obtaining M marks) along with the display of mode, median and mean.

distribution is more evenly spread meaning that there is more uniformity in the distribution of marks. Keeping in mind the above observations, we have defined the the probability of getting marks M as

$$F(M) = \frac{|M-M_0|^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\beta_{neg} |M-M_0|} \theta(M_0-M) + |M-M_0|^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\beta_{pos} |M-M_0|} \theta(M-M_0)}{Z} \tag{33}$$

This function can be seen analogous to the Maxwell Boltzmann distribution of energy. The number of particles that can be distributed among different energy levels with energy E to $E + dE$ can be considered to be directly proportional to $\frac{E^{1/2} e^{-E/KT}}{Z}$.

If we simplify equation (33), we will get,

$$F(M) = \frac{|M-M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta |M-M_0|}}{Z} \tag{34}$$

Equation (34) can be considered to be very similar to the Maxwell Boltzmann distribution of speed. Further when we plot the real data, we will clearly be able to draw the similarities between the two in a more graphical representation.

The reason why we have substituted energy in the Boltzmann energy distribution is because marks and energy seem to show analogous behaviour and can also be shown so using the graphical representations of the two. The $|M - M_0|^{1/2}$ term has been considered as the correction factor and can be physically interpreted as the correction introduced for density of states. This is done so that the probability density does not increase linearly with marks for $M > 0$. This is reflective of the observations made in real life data:

- Low Marks: A small percentage of pupils receive extremely low (or negative) grades as a result of guesswork or incomplete information.
- Mid-Range Marks: Because they tackle questions for which they are only marginally prepared, a greater percentage of pupils receive mid-range marks.

- High Marks: Because it takes almost flawless preparation, fewer pupils receive extremely high grades.

Moreover, if we do not take the term $|M - M_0|^{1/2}$, then at $M=0$, the function would have a finite value, suggesting a non-negligible chance of scoring precisely zero. This is frequently unattainable. But since, we are ensuring that the term $M^{1/2}$ is being used in this function, the function becomes zero as the $M \rightarrow 0^+$, thus making a more realistic approach.

$|M - M_0|$ takes care of the negative marking because if we do not take the absolute value, considering the case of negative marking, we will get imaginary numbers which is not possible.

Here, Z is the partition function which can be written as:

$$Z = \sum_{M=-75}^{300} |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta|M-M_0|} \quad (35)$$

Though according to the data collected no student can get the lowest possible marks, but the probability of getting negative marks is not negligible, this is the reason why instead of directly using $|M|^{1/2}$, we have introduced the term M_0 which ensures the shift in the probability distribution function. For values of $M_0 > 0$, the function will shift towards the right. Similarly, if we take the value of $M_0 < 0$ then the function will shift towards the negative region. But if we want the function to start plotting at $M=0$, we take the value of $M_0 = 0$.

The factor β has been taken as β_{pos} and β_{neg} for the positive and negative regions respectively. This has been done to ensure the asymmetric decay in the positive and negative regions. The negative region will show a greater decay than the positive region and it goes to zero after a certain negative value. Thus, two different β factors have been considered.

Another important part of the function that has been mentioned in equation (33) is the Heaviside step function $\theta(x)$. The Heaviside step function is a mathematical function used to switch the behaviour of a function based on the value of x . Therefore, we can write:

$$\theta(x) = 1; x \geq 0 \text{ and } \theta(x) = 0; x < 0 \quad (36)$$

Based on this definition we can say that $\theta(M - M_0)$ ensures only the first term of equation (33) is applicable for $M \geq M_0$ whereas $\theta(M_0 - M)$ ensures only the first term of equation (33) is applicable for $M < M_0$. Thus, we are able to achieve the function that we have achieved through the real data set.

Figure 10: Marks distribution at $M_0 = -12$ and $\beta_{neg} = 2.85$ but for different values of β_{pos}

Figure-10 has been plotted to understand how the marks distribution occurs at different values of β . The real exam data (figure-9) has been closely found to resemble the bell-shaped curve that we have obtained in this graph. Thus, Maxwell Boltzmann distribution law can be applied to real marks distribution very well especially for large scale exams. The Boltzmann factor $e^{-\beta|M-M_0|}$ is the one determining that at higher scores, the percentage of students will decrease. From the comparison of β , we can say that if β is greater, that is for difficult examination, the graph is narrower and a higher peak is achieved. This implies that for difficult exam very small number of students achieve good marks and the ones who are really well prepared gets higher scores. This behaviour of marks distribution against various difficulty levels can be compared to the way particles behave at various temperatures. The probability of particles existing in higher energy states becomes less as we increase the temperature. The calibration of the y scale can be understood as follows: if 10 lakhs students are participating then 0.025 on the scale would mean 25,000.

Using the function of marks thus defined, we can calculate various aspects of the same. The average or expected marks can be calculated as follows:

$$\mu = \frac{1}{Z} \sum_{M=-75}^{300} M F(M) = \frac{1}{Z} \sum_{M=-75}^{300} M |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta_{neg}|M-M_0|} \theta(M_0 - M) + |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta_{pos}|M-M_0|} \theta(M - M_0) \quad (37)$$

The expected marks of the students is very crucial because it helps us in understanding the overall performance of the students and thus, helps us in evaluating our performance relative to the accomplishments of all the other students.

The expectation value of M and M^2 are $\frac{1}{Z} \sum_{M=-75}^{300} M |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta |M - M_0|}$ and $\frac{1}{Z} \sum_{M=-75}^{300} M^2 |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta |M - M_0|}$ respectively.

3.3 Percentile Calculation

As we have already mentioned, the percentile of a student is the ratio of the number of students who have scored less than or equal to the marks to the total number of students who have appeared for the examination. According to the definition,

$$P(M) = \sum_{m'=-75}^{M'} F(m') = \sum_{m'=-75}^{M'} \frac{|M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta |M - M_0|}}{Z} \tag{38}$$

The above equation has been obtained after substituting the value of $F(m)$ from equation (34). Taking the value of $Z = \sum_{M=-75}^{300} |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta |M - M_0|}$, we get equation (36) as:

$$P(M) = \frac{\sum_{m'=-75}^{M'} |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta |M - M_0|}}{\sum_{m=-75}^{300} |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta |M - M_0|}} \tag{39}$$

The percentile function here, is interpreted as a ratio of cumulative probability divided by the normalization factor.

Figure 11: Plot of Relative Ranking $R(m)/Y$ versus Marks (m) for different values of β , $M_0 = -12$

3.4 Rank Estimation

Let the rank of a student with marks M be $R(M)$ and the percentile score is $P(M)$, and the total number of students participating in the examination is Y . Rank of the student with marks M is given as:

$$R(M) = Y[1 - P(M)/100] \tag{40}$$

Using equation (39) in (40), one gets,

$$\frac{R(M)}{Y} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{m'=-75}^{M'} |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta |M - M_0|}}{\sum_{m=-75}^{300} |M - M_0|^{1/2} e^{-\beta |M - M_0|}} / 100 \tag{41}$$

Figure-11 shows that, at smaller marks, the rank drops steeply. At the extreme values of marks, there is saturation achieved. The graph approaches 1 at low marks meaning most students are clustered at lower marks. There is a steep decline in the region of marks from -50 to 100 . A very small change in percentile will cause a huge change in the rank if the student scores marks in that range. The curves approach very small values at higher marks, which means that very few students are able to reach that level.

4. Real Data Simulation

Though the Scores-versus-Percentile-versus-Rank data from the NTA would have been the most authentic information to carry out our study, but unfortunately, it does not make the results public. The data used in this analysis was taken from JEE Mains datasets available through some websites

[12, 13]. The method of their collection of data is not known but it can be inferred that since they have access to the results of many students, they can create a general trend from those scores anonymously.

Figure-9 is based on this dataset. This figure shows the probability of students attaining M marks. This gives us an insight to the various aspects of an exam model. As can be seen from the graph, the mode i.e., the most frequently occurring marks of the distribution is 61.00 while the average of the distribution is 155.45. This helps us in understanding the marks that the majority of the students obtain and prepare the students accordingly. If we follow the general trend of the graph, then we can see that most of the marks are clustered in the mid-range, implying that maximum students score marks in that range. The graph tapers at the two extreme ends – lesser population in higher scores and similarly, a smaller number of people obtain very low scores. The graph does resemble a bell shape which supports the theory that we have deduced.

Figure 12: Plot of Percentile versus Marks for actual data.

Figure-12 shows the plot of percentile versus marks based on the dataset that has been obtained [12, 13]. This plot is very similar to the ones that we have obtained from our models. At lower marks, the curve rises sharply, becoming less steep as marks increase. A slight rise in marks at the lower end causes large increase in percentile score. Although there are many data points available, the study would have been more informative if we could properly distinguish between the different shifts of the examination so that the difficulty level parameter and other factors around it could be studied. The study cannot be properly made because of the lack of data available. Differences between the actual data and the theoretical model point to the presence of other variables that may be included in subsequent improvements, including changes in paper difficulty-level, adaptive normalization, and trends in student preparation. This model could further be extended to other competitive exams and its dataset can also be studied in a similar way.

5. Conclusion

From the above discussion, we can infer that the probability of a student scoring M marks can be plotted using the Maxwell Boltzmann distribution. Since there can be a similarity drawn between the students in an examination and the number of particles in a system, we can define a function for examinees similar to the distribution. This scheme can be very effective in predicting the percentile and the rank of a student and also their chances of getting admission to various courses, based on previous year trends. This model also calculates the average preparation level and the most probable marks which will help the institutes to prepare students more effectively based on their relative stand in the crowd. The difficulty level parameter which has been introduced helps the academic educators to analyse a paper and train their students better. Because of the lack of availability of data, the model has several shortcomings. But the model could be made more efficient if the government sources released their data. The model that has been formulated as a generalized model, implying that it can be extended to other national and international level examinations like CUET UG, NEET, SAT, etc. Because of its universality, it can also be applied to various school and college examinations. If the teachers and the professors have access to the marks of the students across various examinations, then they can use it in the functions that have been used in the model. The results obtained can be used to analyse the performance of the students depending on the examination difficulty level. The study of various graphs mentioned in this model, when applied to real data, can prove to be of assistance all across the field of education. The model could be made to better analyse the performance by understanding the effect of other parameters like time constraint and psychological state of the student on the day of examination. In the future, if the shortcomings of the model are dealt with, this model would indeed prove to be useful to various sections of the society.

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